

Correlation, path-coefficient and genetic divergence for agro-morphological traits among coffee hybrids grown under coffee berry disease prone environments

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge of interrelationship among economic characters and genetic diversity helps plant breeders in outlying efficient breeding strategies for development of high yielding coffee cultivars. Eight selected coffee hybrids originally developed from crosses between Ethiopian Arabica coffee diversity and two commercial check varieties were tested for component associations and quantifying genetic divergence among genotypes at two sites in highland coffee growing agro-ecology of Southwestern Ethiopia during 2013/14 and 2014/15 cropping seasons. Data were collected for 14 agro-morphological traits. Combined ANOVA, Correlation, path and genetic divergence analyses were used to interpret the data. Significant genetic variation existed among the hybrids and check varieties in almost all traits. The genotypic correlations were higher than the phenotypic, indicating a prevailing influence of the genotypic over the environmental effects in the relationship between significant traits; the same sign indicates their tendencies to reinforce each other. Both the correlation and path coefficient analyses indicated that trait canopy diameter followed by length of primary branches and internodes length of primary branches appeared to be the first order traits for higher berry yield in Arabica coffee and priority should be given in selection due to strong associations as well as high magnitudes of direct effects on berry yield. Genetic distance estimates using the morphological traits showed moderately high genetic distance. Cluster analysis based on the distance measures grouped the ten genotypes in to three main clusters. The hybrid check variety Ababuna clustered alone in separate cluster, while the variety check 74110 and the hybrid HC1 clustered together. The other seven test hybrids also clustered together in shared sub-clusters according to their pedigree. The study demonstrated minimum variation or more similarity among the test hybrids as indicative of genetic consistence and can be exploited for deployment of a new hybrid variety. On other hand, the most dissimilar were the hybrid check (Ababuna) and variety check (74110) having a high genetic distance can be used for hybridization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee production is fundamental for over 50 developing countries, for which it is the main foreign currency earner (Agwanda *et al.*, 1997). Coffee (*Coffea arabica* L.) is the most important commercial crop in the national economy of Ethiopia. In Ethiopia, coffee is mainly grown in three altitude zones viz., the high altitude (over 1750 m above sea level), the medium altitude (between 1550 m and 1750m above sea level) and the low altitude (below 1550 m above sea level (Bayetta *et al.*, 2000).

However, production across these climatic ranges is seriously constrained by diseases, especially coffee berry disease (CBD) at highland (Eshetu, 2000) and the yield loss also reported to exceed 40% at highland environment (Eshetu and Girma, 1992). The use of resistant variety provides a permanent solution and guarantees stable cash income to grower as compared to chemical control (Bayetta *et al.*, 2000). Many improved CBD resistant hybrid coffee genotypes have recently (Behailu *et al.*, 2008) become available in Ethiopia which have been advanced by Jima agricultural research center (JARC) for breeding and production purposes. As a new promising coffee varieties are continuously being developed through hybridization, there is need to determine the level and source of morphological variations within and between new and existing coffee varieties (Gichimu and Omondi, 2010). The genetic consistency within varieties is also essential to quality assurance for any agricultural products (Hue, 2005), apart from exploiting the existing genetic diversity.

The knowledge of the association of characters with yield at genetic and phenotypic level is of great importance to the breeder for making an improvement and outlying efficient breeding strategies (Ahmed *et al.*, 2010) in a complex character like been yield which showed little response to direct selection.

Path coefficient analysis, on the other hand, is more useful for partitioning of direct and indirect causes of the genetic correlation and also enables breeders to compare the component factors on the basis of their relative contributors as developed and outlined by Wright (1921) and revised by Dewey and Lu (1959).

The genetic correlation explains the additive (breeding value) component of genetic variation and the environmental correlation values signify the environmental deviations of the non-heritable components of variation, so both are combined together to give phenotypic correlation (Falconer,1989).The phenotypic correlation and the genetic correlation between two characters may not be of the same sign if the environmental correlation is significant and acting against the genetic correlation (Hoi *et al.*,1999). By having this information the selection of high yielding genotypes at early stage of breeding in perennial crop like coffee would allow the development of new cultivars

by reduced cost (Anim- Kwapong and Adomako, 2010; Wardiana and Pranowo, 2014).

The genetic correlation is important to examine the underlying cause of phenotypic correlation and can be manipulated to improve the efficiency of selection (Kearsey and Pooni, 1996). However, the available reports on character association among yield and its components on both Arabica and Robusta coffee are mostly based on either phenotypic correlation alone (Ameha,1982) or with genotypic correlation estimated at a single environment/location (Walyaro and Van der Vossen,1979; Leroy,1994; Cilas *et al.*,1998;Olika *et al.*, 2011;Wardiana and Pranowo, 2014). The few recently available reports on genetic and environment correlation which based on across locations information are mostly on Robusta coffee (Marandu *et al.*,2004; Ferrao *et al.*,2008a; Anim-Kwapong and Adomako, 2010). Marandu *et al.*(2004) and Anim- Kwapong and Adomako (2010) reported that the strong relation of coffee yield with vegetative characters such as plant girth, height, canopy diameter and primary branches with different magnitudes of genotypic and phenotypic correlations. Marandu *et al.* (2004), Srinivasan (1980) and Wardiana and Pranowo (2014) also partitioned these associations into direct and indirect effect on coffee yield. Hence, such kind of information using across environment data could be gainful in breeding for yield in Arabica coffee under our condition.

Cluster analysis helps to understand the genetic relation among the breeding lines or hybrids and also to facilitate the selection of genetically diverse parents in hybridization program resulting in considerable amount of heterosis and wide range of segregation. Genetic divergence has been studied in coffee using morphological markers (Gichimu and Omondi, 2010; Guedes *et al.*, 2013) and such kind of studies are also provide genetic information and opportunity for plant breeders to develop new high-yielding crop varieties (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2014). The recently advanced coffee hybrids established at multi-site trials in highland coffee growing agro-ecology of Ethiopia are characterized as resistant to coffee berry disease that have not yet been identified.

Therefore, the study was taken to investigate the extent of genetic diversity through some agromorphological traits and to determine the interrelationship among these important agromorphological traits at genotypic and phenotypic levels, and quantify their direct and indirect influence on berry yield in selected hybrids of Arabica coffee for utilization in selection and facilitate variety releasing program for Coffee Berry Disease prone Environments in Southwestern Ethiopian.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study sites

The study was conducted in 2013/14 and 2014/15 production seasons at two different sites in Gera district of the Southwestern region of Ethiopia. The study sites represent the highland humid coffee growing agro-ecology and are well known as hot spot for coffee berry disease (CBD). The sites were Gera Research Station and on-farm location around the station. The station is situated at 7°46'N latitude, 36°26'E longitude and an altitude of 1974 m above sea level (asl) with a mean annual rainfall of about 1880 mm. Average daily minimum and maximum temperatures are about 10.4 and 24.5°C, respectively. The soil around Gera station is dominantly by Acrisols and Nitoso with P^H of 5-6 and medium to high exchangeable cation (Paulos and Tesfaye, 2000). The On-farm site shares most of the macro-environmental variables of the former site.

2.2. Germplasm, experimental design and field management

Eight experimental coffee hybrids that were originally developed by crossing among germplasm primarily collected for their resistance to CBD (Table 1) were used for the study. The hybrids were and selected from previous screening trials for showing better resistance to

CBD, desirable cup quality and high yielding potential (Behailu *et al.*, 2008). Two commercial checks Ababuna (Hybrid check, here after referred as HCCK) selected from long-term hybridization program and 74110 (Variety check, VCK) originating from individual tree selection were also included in the trial for comparison.

The hybrids were established using a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications at each site in July, 2008. Each plot comprised of sixteen coffee trees planted in two rows for each genotype. The spacing between rows and trees within the rows were 2 m by 2 m. Each experiment was surrounded by one row of border trees to provide competition to peripheral plots and at the same time to protect the plots from wind and wild life damage. Fertilizer and crop management practices were uniformly applied at both sites throughout the trial periods as to the recommendation (Endale *et al.*, 2008). At each sites, one *Susbania* *susbanshade* tree was established to provide shade for every four coffee trees, however at early growth stages the coffee seedlings were uniformly protected from direct sun light by small grass shelters up until the shade trees have come to provide the appropriate shading level. All the coffee trees were maintained in single stem pruning system to maintain uniformity within as well as among plots.

Table 1. Description of the coffee hybrids and commercial checks used for the study

Entry No	Code- name	Cross*	Cross categories†
1	HC¶1	P ₁ X P ₂	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
2	HC2	P ₁ X P ₃	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
3	HC3	P ₁ X P ₄	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
4	HC4	P ₅ X P ₂	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
5	HC5	P ₃ X P ₅	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
6	HC6	P ₃ X P ₂	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
7	HC7	P ₁ X P ₅	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
8	HC8	P ₄ X P ₂	CBD res +Q x CBD res +Q
9	Ababuna(HCCK)	hybrid check	CBD res x high yielder
10	74110 (VCK)	variety check	CBD res

* P= Parent

† CBD res = CBD resistant; Q = good quality; HY = high yielder; ¶ HC = Hybrid coffee

2.3. Evaluation of the hybrids for yield and various agro-morphological traits

In this study a number of important yield and agronomic traits were assessed. Fifteen agro-morphological traits were measured for two consecutive years at third and fourth full bearing stages of the coffee trees using eight central trees in each plot. The variables measured included plant height (PH; cm), measured from ground level to tip of the tree; stem girth (GIRTH; cm), taken at 5cm above the ground; number of primary branches produced (NPB), obtained by direct counting the branches; percent fruit bearing primary branches (BP; %), obtained by the ratio between the number primary branches produced and the number of fruiting branches from four selected primary branches per tree; canopy diameter (CD; cm), measured as an average value of

the length of each tree in east-west and north-south direction; number of main stem nodes (SNN), obtained by direct counting of the tree; internode length on the main stem (ILS; cm), obtained by the ratio between the total height of above the first primary and their respective total number of nodes minus one per tree; number of branch nodes (BNN), obtained by direct counting in the selected branches; percent fruit bearing nodes (BN; %), estimated as the percent of the number of nodes with berries on four selected primaries per tree; internode length of primary branches (ILB; cm), obtained by the ratio between the length of the branches and the number of nodes of the selected primary branches; length of primary branches (LPB; cm), measured in four selected branches per tree from middle part of the tree; number of secondary branches (SB), obtained by direct counting in four selected branches; number of berries

from two heavily fruit bearing nodes per branch (BeNo), counted after six months of flowering and obtained by direct counting the number of fruits from two heavily bearing nodes per branches in four selected branches; berry yield (YLD; kg tree⁻¹), recorded as the weight of fresh cherries harvested from sixteen trees in plot basis and converted to berry yield per tree. Data averaged across plots for each seasons across locations were used for statistical analysis.

Growth traits (PH, GIRTH, NPB, SNN, CD, ILS, LPB, BNN, ILB and SB) evaluated after the end of each harvest year ensuring the recovery of trees and before the start of flush re-growth (February /March, in this case). Yield or Productive traits (BP, BN and BeNo) evaluated after six months of main flowering of each year per site (July/ August, in this case). Yield (YLD) recorded as the weight of fresh cherries harvested per tree on plot basis for two production years from October to January each year per site for the period of 2013/14 to 2014/15.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

To compare genotype means, each trait was analyzed separately using Proc GLM with the MIXED procedure of SAS, with over all mean and genotypes considered fixed effect factors and all other factors considered random (Littell *et al.*, 1996; SAS Institute Inc, 2008).

Genotypic and phenotypic correlations were estimated for each pair of traits across environments using a multivariate extension of the mixed model after Holland (2006) and path coefficient analysis was conducted for traits which have shown significant genetic association with berry yield according to Dewey and Lu (1959).

The genetic correlation coefficient was estimated using the following formula:

$$rg_{12} = \frac{\sigma g_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 g_1 \times \sigma^2 g_2}}$$

where, σg_{12} is the estimated genotypic covariance between traits 1 and 2 and $\sigma^2 g_i$ is estimated genotypic variance for trait i ($i = 1$ or 2).

The phenotypic correlation coefficient was estimated as:

$$rp_{12} = \frac{\sigma p_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 p_1 \times \sigma^2 p_2}} \\ = \frac{\sigma g_{12} + \sigma g e_{12} + \sigma e_{12}}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 g_1 + \sigma^2 g e_1 + \sigma^2 e_1} \sqrt{\sigma^2 g_2 + \sigma^2 g e_2 + \sigma^2 e_2}}$$

where, σp_{12} and $\sigma g e_{12}$ are the phenotypic covariance

and genotype-by-environment covariance, respectively, between traits 1 and 2, and $\sigma^2 p_i$ and $\sigma^2 g e_i$ are the phenotypic and genotype-by-environment variance for character i . The estimated correlation coefficients were tested against their approximate standard errors (SE) by standard t-test by checking its validity or comparability with the 95% confidence interval estimation procedure of Lynch & Walsh (1998) not to lose much information in declaring the significant level for each pair of trait associations.

Means of each agro-morphological trait was standardized before subjecting it to the multivariate analysis as was suggested by Milligan and Cooper (1987). The standardized data of fourteen morpho-agronomic traits were then used as an input for the Euclidian distances computing and cluster analysis. The distances were computed according to Anderberg (1973) and Sneath and Sokal (1973) using SAS software package SAS (2008). A dendrogram was constructed from the distance matrix using an agglomerative, hierarchical cluster classification technique with average linkage strategy.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Analysis of variance

There was non-significant genotype with environment/location interaction (data not shown) for almost all measured characteristics. For this reason, the genotype by environment interaction effects were assumed to be minor consequence in correlation coefficient (trait associations) and multivariate analysis results using across-environments data and the genotypic mean value across environments, respectively.

Differences among genotypes were significant ($P < 0.01$) for almost all traits across environments (Table 2) demonstrating that there is genetic variability among the genotypes studied. The experimental coefficients of variation (CV) were within the range 6.92-28.07% (Table 2), which is considered acceptable for experiments in perennial cultures such as coffee (Ferrão *et al.*, 2008b). The Commercial hybrid variety HCCK got the highest mean value in most of morphological traits studied, especially significantly highest for plant vigor traits (plant height, girth and canopy diameter) and vegetative traits (length of primary branches, internodes length of main stem and internodes length of primary branches), though it was not significantly different from the test hybrids for several traits including berry yield. On other hand, the commercial variety check (VCK) recorded lower mean value in all traits studied (Table 2). Hybrid HC5 was also the second least recorder next to variety check for most of traits evaluated.

Table 2. Genotype means, coefficient of variation (CV) of eight experimental hybrids and two check varieties for 14 agro-morphological traits evaluated in four Gera environments in southwestern Ethiopia

Hybrid	PH	Girth	LPB	NPB	SNN	CD	ILS	BP	BNN	ILB	BN	SB	BeNo	YLD
HC1	269.3b†	6.36a	83.35bcd	76.00a	42.72abc	190.04b	5.92bc	83.47abc	20.75d	4.09b	43.72abc	6.01ab	21.99abcd	5.37ab
HC2	271.7b	5.82bc	82.53cd	83.30a	42.85abc	185.91bc	5.87c	79.96d	21.13cd	3.95bcd	46.11a	5.73bc	23.30a	5.82a
HC3	264.7bc	5.70cd	82.32cd	82.50a	42.79abc	183.25cd	5.81cd	81.99bcd	21.95abcd	3.76de	44.82abc	6.09ab	22.33abc	5.12ab
HC4	272.1b	6.00b	85.46bc	84.30a	43.81a	183.67bcd	5.71cd	83.21abc	22.58ab	3.73de	43.34abc	5.14cd	21.57bcde	5.72a
HC5	249.4cd	5.04e	76.04e	84.30a	43.50ab	166.98e	5.24ef	82.31bcd	21.33cd	3.61ef	43.07abc	4.16e	20.86cde	3.51c
HC6	279.0b	6.02b	87.84b	77.8bc	41.40c	189.70b	6.25b	83.96ab	22.25abc	4.00bc	38.25d	4.32de	20.49de	4.91ab
HC7	252.0c	5.55d	79.91de	81.30ab	41.95abc	178.50d	5.51de	82.70bc	21.33cd	3.79cde	45.58ab	5.7bc	21.94abcd	4.63b
HC8	277.7b	5.88bc	82.67cd	84.20a	43.86a	179.66cd	5.90c	81.18cd	21.47bcd	3.88bcd	42.16c	4.85de	20.32e	4.97ab
HCCK	311.2a	6.39a	103.26a	78.10bc	41.70bc	211.46a	6.96a	85.59a	22.96a	4.57a	42.19c	6.63a	22.64ab	4.84ab
VCK	235.1d	4.96e	71.98f	77.00bc	41.60bc	161.50e	5.13f	81.48bcd	21.06cd	3.42f	42.50bc	5.01cd	20.85cde	3.31c
LSD (5%)	15.90	0.26	4.52	4.38	2.00	6.45	0.34	2.72	1.24	0.23	3.25	0.9	1.59	1.00
CV%	7.31	5.60	6.67	6.64	5.74	4.34	7.26	4.05	7.02	7.20	9.24	19.47	9.05	25.43
F-test	**	**	**	**	NS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	**

Significance level: NS, non-significant; *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01

† Means for the same trait followed by the same letter were not significantly different P = 0.05

PH, plant height (cm); GIRTH, stem girth (cm); NPB, number of primary branches per tree; SNN, number of main stem nodes; CD, canopy diameter (cm); ILS, internode length on the main stem (cm); LPB, length of primary branches (cm); BP, percent fruit bearing primary branches per tree (%); BNN, number of primary branch nodes; ILB, internode length of primary branches (cm); BN, percent fruit bearing nodes per primary branch (%); SB, number of secondary branches per primary branch; BeNo, number of berries in two heavily bearing nodes per primary branch; YLD, berry yield (kg tree⁻¹)

3.2. Genotypic and Phenotypic Correlations

The genotypic (r_G) and phenotypic (r_P) correlation coefficients between yield and vegetative traits across four environments are shown in Table 3. The berry yield had highly significant positive correlation with stem girth, canopy diameter (CD), plant height (PH), internodes length of main stem (ILS), length of primary branches (LPB), internodes length of primary branches (ILB) and number of secondary branches (SB) except for number of primary branches (NPB), number of stem nodes per tree (SNN), percent bearing primaries per tree (BP), number of nodes per primary branch (BNN), percent bearing nodes (BN) and number of berries in two heavily bearing nodes per branch (BeNo) suggesting that selection for these significantly associated traits can result in more productive coffee trees. The degree of association was highest between berry yield per tree (YLD) and girth ($r_G=0.91^{**}$) followed by canopy diameter ($r_G=0.69^{**}$), plant height ($r_G=0.64^*$), number of secondary branches ($r_G=0.62^*$), internodes length of main stem ($r_G=0.57^*$), length of primary branches ($r_G=0.54^*$) and internodes length of primary branches ($r_G=0.51^*$). The significant positive genetic associations between yields and girth, canopy diameter agrees with previous findings in Arabica coffee (Walyaro, 1983; Cilas *et al.*, 1998) and with plant height and canopy diameter (Olika *et al.*, 2011), and girth and canopy diameter in Robusta coffee (Anim-Kwapong and Adomako, 2010). The strong association of these plant vigor traits (plant height, canopy diameter and stem girth) with yield may be related with an increased ability to escape adverse conditions that may subsequently lower yield. On other hand, the presence of significant and positive genetic correlation of some of these characters (number of nodes per primary branch, percent bearing primaries per tree and number of berries in two heavily bearing nodes per branch) with most of important growth traits (plant height, girth, canopy diameter, internodes length of main stem, length of primary branches and internodes length of primary branches) and lack of negative correlation with yield except percent bearing primaries per tree (though non-significant) will not have undesirable

consequences in selection aimed at increased coffee yield.

Berry yield had significantly positive phenotypic correlations with all seven growth traits that exhibited significant genetic correlations but its magnitude is lower revealing their apparent association was under genetic control. Apart from this, all significant correlations combination at both genetic and phenotypic level exhibited the same sign indicates lack of contrary action among effects.

For variables to be meaningfully important as selection criteria for yield, the variables should be positively and significantly correlated among themselves (Marandu *et al.*, 2004). In the present investigation, all the above seven traits that significantly and positively correlated with yield also showed significant and positive associations among themselves at both correlation levels except for plant height (PH), internodes length of main stem (ILS) and secondary branches (SB) where some of their associations were only at genetic level indicating little environmental effects involved in their associations and that genetic cause were more responsible for their associations. Similar relationships among these traits have been reported by Marandu *et al.* (2004) in Robusta coffee. The broad sense heritability of these traits other than secondary branches (SB) was also high (data not shown). The above six traits, therefore, should be preserved in Arabica coffee breeding programs for improvement of yield.

Generally, estimates of genotypic correlation coefficients were found to be higher than their respective phenotypic correlation coefficients (Table 3), which are in agreement with the results of Ferrao *et al.* (2008a). Significant genotypic and phenotypic associations were observed between several pairs of traits. The present results suggest that the influence of the genetic factors on character association was greater than of the environmental factors as a result of the modifying effects of the environment in character association at the gene level (Pandey, 1981). Similar dominance of genetic factors in the inter-character relationships was reported by Ferrao *et al.* (2008a).

Table 3. Estimates of genotypic (above diagonal) and phenotypic (below diagonal) correlation coefficients among various plant traits in some Arabica coffee hybrids and commercial check varieties across four Gera environments

Traits	PH	Girth	NPB	SNN	CD	ILS	LPB	BNN	ILB	SB	BP	BN	BeNo	YLD
PH	1	0.91**	-0.22	-0.19	0.97**	0.98**	0.99**	0.94**	0.94*	0.53*	0.86**	-0.47*	0.54*	0.64*
GIRTH	0.60**	1	-0.31	-0.05	0.94**	0.89**	0.86**	0.49*	0.92**	0.58*	0.65*	-0.14	0.70*	0.91**
NPB	0.24*	-0.02	1	0.93**	-0.33	-0.36	-0.21	0.13	-0.37**	-0.29	-0.66*	0.60*	-0.28	0.27
SNN	0.25*	0.14	0.46**	1	-0.35	-0.29	-0.34	-0.3	-0.40	-0.44	-0.85*	0.62*	-0.36	0.37
CD	0.82**	0.72**	0.01	0.09	1	0.99**	0.98**	0.80**	0.99**	0.70**	0.86*	-0.22	0.90*	0.69**
ILS	0.03	0.54**	-0.06	-0.27**	0.75**	1	0.99**	0.84**	0.98**	0.61*	0.91**	-0.48*	0.55*	0.57*
LPB	0.81**	0.59**	-0.03	0.06	0.82**	0.72**	1	0.90**	0.90**	0.57*	0.96**	-0.41*	0.15	0.54*
BNN	0.22	0.32**	0.01	0.13	0.22	0.15	0.50**	1	0.72*	0.15	0.79**	-0.57*	-0.01	0.38
ILB	0.02	0.53**	-0.01	-0.03	0.78**	0.76**	0.78**	-0.08	1	0.69**	0.96**	-0.32	0.77*	0.51*
SB	0.10	0.34*	-0.18	-0.02	0.25	0.12	0.33*	0.30**	0.15	1	0.34	0.82*	0.89*	0.62*
BP	0.08	0.26*	-0.07	-0.13	0.26*	0.08	0.30*	0.30**	0.10	0.17	1	-0.62*	-0.06	-0.07
BN	-0.06	-0.19	0.09	0.01	-0.08	-0.13	-0.05	-0.24*	0.05	0.06	-0.05	1	0.91*	0.39
BeNo	0.26*	0.12	0.06	-0.04	0.24*	0.20	0.27*	0.06	0.27*	0.18	0.16	0.42**	1	0.97
YLD	0.34**	0.46**	0.19	0.14	0.34*	0.24*	0.32*	0.19	0.32*	0.16	0.16	0.20*	0.23*	1

Significance level: *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01. PH, plant height (cm); GIRTH, stem girth (cm); NPB, number of primary branches per tree; SNN, number of main stem nodes; CD, canopy diameter (cm); ILS, internode length on the main stem (cm); LPB, length of primary branches (cm); BNN, number of primary branch nodes; ILB, internode length of primary branches (cm); SB, number of secondary branches per primary branch; BP, percent fruit bearing primary branches per tree (%); BN, percent fruit bearing nodes per primary branch (%); BeNo, number of berries in two heavily bearing nodes per primary branch; YLD, berry yield (kg tree⁻¹)

3.3. Path Analysis

Results of path coefficient analysis (Table 4) based on genotypic correlation of all the agro-morphological traits indicated that, among the traits, canopy diameter (CD) had the highest direct positive effect (4.33) on berry yield per tree (YLD) followed by length of primary branches (2.64) and internodes length of primary branches (1.00). This in any one of the above traits might directly contribute increased berry yield. Highest negative direct effect on yield was exhibited by traits internodes length of main stem (-7.89) followed by number of secondary branches (-0.27). These two traits had significant positive genetic correlations with berry yield ($r_G=0.57^*$ and $r_G=0.62^*$, respectively) but had negative or negligible direct effect on berry yield in which their indirect positive effect via canopy diameter and length of primary branches might be the cause. The latter were due to relatively high direct effect on yield and their respective significant and positive genetic correlations with internodes length of main

stem ($r_G=0.99^{**}$ and 0.98^{**}), and number of secondary branches ($r_G=0.70^{**}$, 0.57^*). The present results are consistent partly with the findings of Marandu *et al.* (2004) for plant height, canopy diameter and girth in Robusta coffee, Srinivasan (1980) for length of primary branches and internodes length of primary branches and Wardiana and Pranowo (2014) for plant height but contradict for canopy diameter who reported as negative selection criteria in Arabica coffee. Differential finding could be attributed to difference in studied materials, environments (in type and number) and number of characters included in the analysis. The indirect positive effect of plant height, stem girth, internodes length of main stem, internodes length of primary branches and number of secondary branches on berry yield, mostly were through canopy diameter and length of primary branches, respectively (Table 4). Therefore, these two traits must be considered if selection is made through plant height, stem girth, internodes length of main stem, internodes length of primary branches and number of secondary branches.

Table 4. Estimate of direct effect (bold face and diagonal) and indirect effects (off diagonal) at genotypic level in eight hybrid coffee and two commercial checks across four Gera environments

Traits	PH	Girth	CD	ILS	LPB	ILB	SB	r_G
PH	0.05	0.72	4.20	-7.73	2.61	0.94	-0.15	0.64*
GIRTH	0.05	0.79	4.07	-7.02	2.27	0.92	-0.16	0.91**
CD	0.05	0.74	4.33	-7.81	2.59	0.99	-0.19	0.69**
ILS	0.05	0.70	4.29	-7.89	2.61	0.98	-0.17	0.57*
LPB	0.05	0.68	4.25	-7.81	2.64	0.90	-0.16	0.54*
ILB	0.05	0.72	4.29	-7.73	2.37	1.00	-0.19	0.51*
SB	0.03	0.46	3.03	-4.81	1.50	0.69	-0.27	0.62*

Significance level: * $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$; PH, plant height (cm); GIRTH, stem girth (cm); CD, canopy diameter (cm); ILS, internode length on the main stem (cm); LPB, length of primary branches (cm); ILB, internode length of primary branches (cm); SB, number of secondary branches per primary branch

3.4. Genetic divergence analysis

Genetic divergence among the pair of component genotypes in the ten hybrids including check varieties quantified using Euclidian distance as dissimilarity/similarity measure showed (Table 5) relatively high degree of variation ranged from 1.95 (between HC3 and HC7) to 10.04 (between VCK and HCCK), thus, indicating a high genetic diversity among the genotypes. Similar trend of variability were shown in the studies of Guedes *et al.* (2013) in coffee (from 0.44-59.62). The commercial hybrid cultivar (HCCK) and variety check (VCK) were considered the most dissimilar genotypes, with a Euclidian genetic distance of 10.04, followed by the pair combinations coffee hybrid HC5 and HCCK, HC8 and HCCK, HC7 and HCCK, and HC2 and HCCK, which also showed high genetic distances, ranging from 7.25 to 9.53. Mean morphological distance was higher for hybrid check HCCK, followed by variety check VCK, Hybrid HC6 and HC5 while HC3 and HC7

the lowest.

A cluster dendrogram constructed based on morphological distance was used to estimate the genetic diversity among the ten coffee genotypes (Fig.1). The genotypes separated into three main clusters. Seven of the test hybrids clustered together in shared sub-cluster in the first cluster, of which the Hybrid HC3 and HC7, HC4 and HC8 joined closely in the sub clusters, an indication of close relatedness among them and such grouping according to pedigree relationship ensures a more stringent evaluation of the adequacy of the data (Dagne *et al.*, 2013). Hybrid HC5 and check variety (VCK) formed unsupported grouping in the second cluster. This was an indication of more diversity among the genotypes. These two genotypes were not related by pedigree, however, shared almost all low mean value of phenotypic characteristics (Table 2). The hybrid check variety HCCK separated distantly from the other genotypes in Cluster III. The two check varieties, pure line (VCK), hybrid (HCCK) were the most distantly related

genotypes as confirmed in distance matrix (Table 5) and clustered separately. The clustering pattern and the mean morphological distance indicates that low variation within the test hybrids while the observed relatively high variation among genotypes were accounted by the two more dissimilar check varieties. The more similarity of the test hybrids explained by the selection acted up on them as well as on their parents in early evaluation programs for which reasons they have reached to a similarity

levels for most of traits studied, apart from the low genetic basis of Arabica coffee Lashermeset *al.* (1993). However, this would not worry us since the original germplasm sources that have already maintained in the field gene bank are available to broaden their genetic bases to possible extent; rather their minimum variation can be taken as indicative of genetic consistence (Hue, 2005) and exploited for deployment of a new hybrid variety.

Table 5. Estimates of genetic distance based on agro- morphological data for all pair-wise combinations of ten coffee genotypes

Genotype	HC1	HC2	HC3	HC4	HC5	HC6	HC7	HC8	HCKK	VCK
HC1										
HC2	3.87									
HC3	3.36	2.42								
HC4	4.26	3.94	2.60							
HC5	5.99	5.58	4.46	4.61						
HC6	4.65	6.36	5.14	4.67	5.98					
HC7	3.42	3.28	1.95	3.75	3.78	5.18				
HC8	4.30	4.10	3.32	2.73	3.72	4.52	3.88			
HCKK	5.79	7.25	6.47	6.60	9.53	5.73	7.27	7.46		
VCK	6.09	6.42	5.24	6.38	3.46	6.25	3.95	5.58	10.04	
Mean	4.64	4.80	3.89	4.39	5.23	5.39	4.05	4.40	7.35	5.93

Figure 1. Dendrogram of ten coffee genotypes explained by Average linkage cluster analysis based on 14 quantitative traits.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study revealed the presence of high levels of variations for most of agro-morphological traits including berry yield among the newly advanced eight hybrid coffee along with two commercial check varieties of Arabica coffee;

Genotypic are higher than phenotypic correlation, indicating a greater influence of genetic than of environmental factors;

The absence of different signs between genetic and phenotypic associations indicating that the adoption of indirect selection based on significant genotypic association is not affected by the differential response of the environment on the traits involved;

Both the correlation and path coefficient analyses indicated that trait canopy diameter (CD) followed by length of primary branches (LPB) and internodes length of primary branches (ILB) appeared to be the first order traits for higher berry yield in Arabica coffee and priority should be given in selection due to strong associations as well as high magnitudes of direct effects on berry yield;

Cluster analysis using all the 14 different traits grouped ten coffee genotypes into three main clusters. The hybrid check variety Ababuna clustered alone in separate cluster, while the variety check 74110 and the hybrid HC1 clustered together. The other seven test hybrids also clustered together in shared sub-clusters according to their pedigree. This study indicated the presence of high levels of genetic diversity among the coffee genotypes for evaluated traits with major variation contributed by the two check varieties hybrid and pure line. However, more similarity or low variation among test hybrid detected as indicative of genetic consistence and can be exploited for deployment of a new hybrid variety. The most dissimilar ones, the hybrid check (Ababuna) and variety check (74110) having a high genetic distance can be used for hybridization.

Conflicting interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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